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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF HEMODYNAMIC ALTERATIONS
SUITABLE SURGICAL CONDITION BETWEEN SUB-
ARACHNOID BLOCK AND SADDLE BLOCK IN SURGERY OF
TRANS-URETHRAL RESECTION PROSTATE**¹Talha Masood, ²Nimra Raza, ³Maria Raza¹Rawalpindi Medical University²Women Medical College Abbottabad³Islamic International Medical College**Abstract:**

Background and Objective: Regional anesthesia is a method of own choice in TURP (Trans-urethral resection of prostate). The most significant anomaly of this spinal procedure is the danger of hypotension. The aim of this research work is to provide a comparison of the hemodynamic alterations and suitable condition of surgery among saddle block and sub-arachnoid block for trans-urethral resection of prostate.

Methodology: Total 96 patients having age from 50 to 70 years ASA-PS-1 and 2 arranged for transurethral resection of prostate divided into two groups with forty-five patients in every group. The patients of Group-A received spinal and patients of Group-B obtained saddle block. We recorded the blood pressure, heart beat rate and saturation of oxygen for all the patients. We also noted the height of block for patients of both groups. The management of the hypotension carried out with the utilization of the phenylephrine fifty mcg bolus and we noted the complete vasopressor requirement. We also noted down the related complications as syndrome and overload of the volume.

Results: The prevalence of the hypotension and requirement of the vasopressor was very less in the patients of Group-B. We achieved the suitable surgical condition in all the patients of both groups. There was no occurrence of the perforation of bladder, TURP syndrome and overload of the volume.

Conclusion: Trans-urethral resection of prostate is very easy to perform under the saddle block with no hypotension and very short need for the vasopressor.

KEY WORDS: Vasopressor, hypotension, transurethral, methodology, overload, saddle lock, TURP, bladder, occurrence.

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INTRODUCTION:

TURP is very frequent surgery for the patients suffering from benign hyperplasia of prostate. The method of choice in the TURP is the selection of the spinal anesthesia. There is some possibility of the overload of circulation because of unnecessary preoccupation of irrigation solution in the duration of surgical intervention. Lithotomy position obtained to perform this surgery. Anesthesia of spine has the ability to support in blood's peripheral pooling with decreasing the possibility of the overload in circulation and in time discovery of the circulations like the syndrome of the TURP and perforation of the bladder. Some of other benefits of this anesthesia procedure are that it gives analgesia after surgery, decreases the loss of blood in the duration of the surgery and it hinders the requirement for intubation through trachea that can irritate the air passage resulting to coughing of hemorrhage after surgery.

Chemical sympathectomy because of anesthesia through spine covers for two to six dermatomes above the level of sensation. In the patients of elder age with heart diseases vascular resistance may reduce to 25.0% while in healthy patients it may reduce to 15.0% to 18.0%. Keeping in view of all benefits and demerits of the procedures, this research work aimed to provide a comparison of the hemodynamic alterations, need of vasopressor and suitable surgical condition between the sub-arachnoid block and saddle block for trans-urethral resection of prostate surgery.

METHODOLOGY:

This was a comparative prospective research work. Ethical committee of the hospital gave the permission to conduct this research work for eight months. We took the consent of ninety patients from 50 to 70 years of age

of ASA-PS 1 and 2 having volume of prostate from 30 to 80 cc with a duration of surgery from 60 to 90 minutes scheduled for trans-urethral resection of prostate were the part of this research work. The calculation of the size of sample size with minimum thirty patients carried out keeping in view the previous research works. Patients with other serious anomalies were not the part of this research work. Eighteen gauge cannula was in use for the anesthetic method and co-loading of the patients carried out with normal saline at a frequency of six ml per kg per hour. We attached the monitor to calculate the HR (Heart Rate), BP, SPO₂ (Electro-cardiograph and Oxygen Saturation). We divided the population into two groups with forty-five patients in each group. Group-A obtained two milligram of 0.50% bupivacaine with twenty-five gauge needle at L3 to L4 and/or L4 to L5 space of inter-vertebra with the use of midline approach in a position of sitting. Group-B obtained two milligrams hyperbaric 0.50% in similar manner as Group-A and remained in sitting position for ten minutes.

The assessment of the sensory block level carried out by the sensation of the temperature bi-laterally and we noted the height of the block for every patient in both groups. Bromage scale was in use for the testing of the motor block. The evaluation of the operating condition performed by the height of block and suitable relaxation of the muscles of pelvic floor. Storz twenty-four Fr resect scope was in use to perform the TURP by single surgeon. SPSS V.16 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information.

RESULTS:

The comparison of patients of both groups carried out regarding patient's age, their height, weight and total duration of the surgery {Table-1}.

Table 1: Demographic data: Age, Weight, Height, duration of surgery

Variables	Spinal (grp A)		Saddle (grp B)		P-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Age (years)	62.640	3.830	63.330	4.160	0.4160
Weight (Kg)	5393.000	928.000	53.290	9.310	0.7430
Height (cm)	161.840	3.840	162.360	1.710	0.4180
Duration of surgery (min)	82.490	1.530	82.270	1.010	0.4190

The comparison of the baseline DBP, HR, SBP, SPO₂ carried out in the patients of both 2 groups [Table-2].

Table 2: Baseline SBP, DBP, MAP, HR, SpO₂ (Mean ± SD)

Baseline	Group A		Group B		P-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SBP (mmHg)	135.870	3.240	134.270	4.540	0.0600
DBP (mmHg)	84.200	4.780	84.200	5.230	0.2100
MAP (mmHg)	100.400	3.850	99.090	4.430	0.1370
HR (mins)	89.400	7.810	88.400	4.810	0.4670
SpO ₂ (%)	99.870	0.970	99.800	1.010	0.7500

The fall of all these baseline values was less in the patients of Group-B in comparison of the patients of Group-A except HR which was much significant as shown in [Table-3].

Table 3: Maximum Fall of SBP, DBP, MAP in Two Groups

Max BP Change	Group A		Group B		P-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
SBP	26.400	1.470	6.420	4.150	<0.00010
DBP	21.670	4.820	6.760	5.430	<0.00010
MAP	22.270	3.010	6.730	3.960	<0.00010

The overall fall of HR was high in the patients of Group-A (11.840 ± 5.850) in comparison with the patients of Group-B (4.760 ± 2.010) which was also much significant statistically. The requirement of the phenylephrine was much less in Group-B [Table-4]. Table-4 describes the consumption of the phenylephrine in the patients of both 2 groups.

Table 4: Phenylephrine Consumption In Both Groups

Groups	Spinal (Group A)		Saddle (Group B)		P-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Phenylephrine consumption (pg)	120.000	30.900	7.780	2.600	<0.00010

Table 5: Fall Of Heart Rate In Two Groups

Groups	Fall of heart rate	
	Mean	SD
Group A	11.840	5.850
Group B	4.760	2.010
P-value	<0.0001	

DISCUSSION:

There is origination of the pain fibers from prostate, urethra and mucosa of bladder from S-2 to S-4 sacral nerves. The signal of the pain from the distension of bladder moves along with T-11 to the L-2 fibers. The sensation of the stretch of the bladder carried out by parasympathetic fibers of S-2 to the S-4. Greater block level may mask the pain on puncture of capsule of prostate [Table-5]. Spinal anesthesia is a procedure

which is matter of choice in the trans-urethral resection of prostate but block height should not be greater than level of T-10. There are different factors which can impact the block height after spinal anesthesia. Toumiren stated that the amount and concentration of the anesthetics in addition with the position prior and after the injection are very important factors having influence the local anesthetic's distribution. Pitkänen stated that the management of ten milligram of 0.50%

hyperbaric bupivacaine create low fall of blood pressure as compared to other anesthetics. Some other works also utilized two milligram of hyperbaric bupivacaine in this surgery of TURP.

There are also possibilities of the more danger of the absorption of the irrigation fluid in the duration of spinal anesthesia because of fall of the BP in comparison with the general anesthesia. There is quick set up of the saddle block, paralyzed muscles of pelvic and roots of the sacral nerve and block height is very short. Therefore, there is very less chances of the hypotension. Dobson managed spinal anesthesia and GA in the patients of TURP and compared the effectiveness of these procedures. He found that GA creates high hemodynamic disparity after its induction. Bowman provided a comparison of pain after surgery in the patients of TURP after spinal anesthesia and GA and discovered that there is very less requirement of the analgesic after in the group of spinal anesthesia. Blake observed that the loss of the blood was very less in the regional anesthesia as compared to the GA. Gurajala carried out saddle block with one milliliter hyperbaric bupivacaine mixed with fifty mcg fentanyl for the patients who were undergoing for the replacement of the aortic and mitral valve for trans-urethral resection of prostate with no harmful cardiovascular influence. Hartmann discovered 20.0% to 30.0% prevalence of hypotension after the application of spinal anesthesia. Ozmen in his research work compared the epidural, spinal and saddle anesthesia in the duration of the trans-urethral resection prostate. He discovered that intra-operative systolic BP and SPO2 was more stable and achievement of the adequate surgical anesthesia carried out very early with no motor block in the group of saddle block. Jindal in his research work discovered that the fall of HR was very greater (21.0%) after spinal anesthesia in comparison with the epidural (17.0%) and general anesthesia (14.0%). In current research work we found HR was high in Group-A than the Group-B. There are some limitations of this research work as we managed very high dose of the bupivacaine in comparison with the conventional dose in the case of the saddle block, we did not measure the irrigation fluid's absorption, loss of blood and estimation of the sodium of serum.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this research work conclude that TURP is very secure process under the impact of saddle block present with very low possibility of the hypotension and less requirement of the vasopressor.

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